

Digital twins in serial production: a teaching methodology for prototyping in process design

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Abstract

This article deals with the design, integration, and development of a sequence of didactic activities for the proposal of improvements in a serial production problem through the construction of an educational experience inspired by an exercise of digital twins, in which it was possible the combination of playful exercises, simulation, construction and contrast of indicators. Thus, this educational experience followed a methodology that included using a physical prototype of a production plant through a playful activity at the beginning and end of the experience. This activity established the initial conditions and a set of proposals for improving manufacturing processes selected from simulated computational experiments. A robust computational simulation tool made implementing the scenarios in the physical prototype possible. This tool allowed us to obtain a digital representation of the playful activity's environment, enabling us to experiment with different scenarios to enhance serial production. The educational experience was a comprehensive integration of various elements. It combined the physical prototype of the recreational activity, the scenario simulation model, and concepts such as the construction of productivity indicators, the use of prioritization and coordination techniques, and the use of contrast techniques in productivity results. All these elements were crucial in determining significant differences between physical prototypes and simulated scenarios. In conclusion, this article provides a detailed description of the experience in engineering education for developing a working session in a workshop modality with which it is possible to facilitate the teaching-learning process of the concepts of serial production, digital twin, and scenario comparison in academic spaces of industrial production, digital simulation, and rapid prototyping in process design.

Keywords: Digital Twins; Serial Production; Educational Engineering Methodology, Simulation Model, Playful Activity.

1 Introduction

Current trends in engineering education show the use of scale models of factories in academic environments as an element that can benefit the imitation of natural environments through the use of software for the design and management of processes and material flow in production management systems such as ERP, JIT or hybrid among others, which include concepts such as flexibility, volatility, ambiguity, and uncertainty, to encourage the search for solutions to the challenges in the design and management of manufacturing processes, JIT or hybrid among others, which include concepts such as flexibility, volatility, ambiguity, and uncertainty, to encourage the search for solutions to the challenges in the design and management of manufacturing processes by actors involved in research and education processes of these topics (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023).

Thus, it is necessary to implement academic exercises to explain, from the perspective of competitive advantage and value chain strategies, the concepts of mass, serial, and unit production. Mass production, characterized by the manufacture of large quantities of standardized products, is aligned with a cost leadership strategy, allowing companies to reduce costs through economies of scale. Mass production, which involves the creation of batches of similar products, seeks to balance efficiency and flexibility, facilitating customization at certain stages while keeping costs relatively low. Finally, unit production, focused on the creation of unique and highly customized products, is adapted to a differentiation strategy, where the added value and exclusivity of the

product justifies a premium price. In each case, the choice of production method impacts the company's cost structure and value proposition, influencing its competitive position in the market. (Porter, 1985; Porter, 2006; Muther & Hales, 1987).

Consequently, the experience reported in this document contains a serial production model in which batches of similar products are produced in a simulated production plant configured with five manufacturing or transformation processes and placed one after the other (Merengo, Nava, & Pozetti, 1999; Becker & Scholl, 2006), to elaborate a batch of defined or calculated size in advance to the realization of the ludic activity, this process is described in Figure 2, aspect that is sought to be simulated in the same way described to start the changes in the simulation model that provide improvements. (Law & Kelton, 2007)

In this perspective, the development of learning with factory models in academic environments establishes a challenge in the inclusion of changes in a manufacturing process that can be replicated to perform the analysis, monitoring, and evaluation with the use of an appropriate software solution and in coherence with the production management system under study (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023) as in reality, an aspect that can have many different approaches from the educational vision among which the use of learning factories is one of the most expanding in Europe (Abele, y otros, 2015).

Therefore, the definition of a learning factory is established as a learning environment with authentic processes, with multiple process stations that include technical and organizational aspects in a changing environment that resembles a real value chain, with a physical product produced under a didactic concept comprising formal, informal and non-formal learning, in which learners perform learning actions in situ (Abele, y otros, 2015; Abele, 2016).

From this point of view, the learning factory is conceived as a facility for realizing products and processes for academic education, which includes student active participation, an agile environment, and an approach to reality that resembles an authentic simulation (Abele, Tenberg, Wennemer, & Cachay, 2010; Abele, y otros, 2017), which can follow different methodologies for its development (Tisch, y otros, 2013), which with pointing out common aspects that relate in the various learning factory experiences to concepts such as purpose, process, settings, product, didactics, and operating model, as described in the literature about topic Learning Factories (Abele, y otros, 2017; Abele, y otros, 2015; Initiative on European Learning Factories, 2013; Lu, Shpitalni, & Gadh, 1999; Thomar, 2015; Sivard & Lundholm, 2013; Kemény, Beregi, Erdős, & Nacsá, 2013).

Now, it is necessary to recognize that learning factories represent from reality, manufacturing processes that, in turn, have software developed for their planning, monitoring, and control that act with rules adapted to the typical behavior of the system in which it is framed through the definition of the production management system, interaction considered as a robust environment in operations but also inflexible and rigid in the face of changes in the number and diversity of products, in the manufacturing process, or the availability of resources, aspects frequently questionable in the processes of learning and research in manufacturing, limiting the introduction of new technologies, work methods, and personnel training in reality (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023).

Given this industrial reality and its representation with models of learning factories, it is necessary to consider the conception and methodology accepted for the execution of these experiences; it is essential to implement techniques that promote the meeting of learning with the conception of processes and product manufacturing in a didactic environment, aspect possible to perform through the use of digital twins, which is considered as one of the basic techniques for the integration of education with research in digital factories (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023).

Thus, in some studies, it has been possible to include in the development of digital twins in learning factories elements such as the internet of things, planning processes, diagnosis, monitoring, and quality control, as well as the use of a digital for the projection of future and potential activities that represent an improvement or evolution of the exercise for educational and research purposes (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023), aspects that coincide with the methods and objectives of a learning factory.

It is also necessary to highlight that this article coincides with studies (Lutters, 2018) in which the use of digital twins has been tested for the achievement of objectives around the exploration of future scenarios discarding risk, analyzing different perspectives regardless of the information system of one or another production management system (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023) and fostering the integration of students' problem-solving skills with a real and a simulated scenario (Slot & Lutters, 2021), with their corresponding interrelationship regardless of their level and discipline of training.

Thus, the real scenario proposed in this article includes some elements of complexity of reality that are related to uncertainty and adaptability of the processes, which, when represented in the digital model, will allow the analysis and understanding of the effects of decision-making in the introduction of new technologies, changes in the process sequence or evaluation of the addition or subtraction of available resources, (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023) aspect that agrees with the results of other studies that perform processes of this type, and that lead to foresee potential future situations in reality through the digital model (Lutters, 2018).

Finally, this article also incorporates the concept of a digital system in which three components are defined (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023; Slot & Lutters, 2022): the digital twin, the digital master, and the digital prototype, in which the digital twin, includes the current state of the system considering the data and information of the process, the models and methods in use, as well as the tools and techniques used in the monitoring and control aspect which is the focus of this paper, in addition to the digital master which represents the future state of the system, and the digital prototype which allows the exploration and analysis of possible changes in through simulation enabling to establish a measure of differences between the first two components (Lutters & Damgrave, 2023; Slot & Lutters, 2022).

2 Methodology

This article focuses on the description of a learning factory in which a classroom exercise is connected with simulation technologies through the use of an elementary-level digital twin for the generation of competencies in engineering students in Colombia by the requirements for the reduction of manual work and the increase of cognitive, social and emotional and technological competencies foreseen for the year 2030 (Dahl, Tvenge, Assuad, & Martinsen, 2023; Ellingrud, Gupta, & Salguero, 2020).

In which an analysis is made of the skills required in the United States and Western Europe in 2016 and its projection in the change of the proportion of combination for the year 2030 in this same geographical region, which can be summarized as a decrease in manual and physical skills from 48% to 35%, The same as basic cognitive competencies from 12% to 10%, while an increase in higher competencies from 17% to 21%, socioemotional competencies from 12% to 16% and technological competencies from 12% to 19% is required, this last aspect with a strong emphasis on the prospective in industrial engineering education, which is the focus of the development of this article. (Dahl, Tvenge, Assuad, & Martinsen, 2023; Ellingrud, Gupta, & Salguero, 2020).

Based on this competency development, the digital twin design case study followed a methodology that combined two methodologies for the development of learning factories. Six concepts related to learning and

the development of the pedagogical device were formulated: purpose, process, settings, product, didactics, and operating model. (Abele, y otros, 2017; Dahl, Tvenge, Assuad, & Martinsen, 2023)

In addition, the case study included the use of physical prototyping of a production plant for mass production with a push management strategy. Participants must produce a set of fifty similar products with differences in two attributes of the material used. This physical prototype was built in a playful environment where each work team was divided into two subgroups, one in charge of production and the other recording information about the manufacturing process. After the data collection, these are taken to a computer room where the statistical data analysis is performed. A set of indicators is constructed, with which it is possible to build a multidisciplinary simulation model of the game, in which many experiments are performed to determine possible futures and present simulated measures that can be compared with the prototype of the initial game.

Once a more favorable scenario is identified through the comparison of indicators from various simulations, the entire multidisciplinary team comes together to assemble and install this scenario. This collective effort is followed by a run of fifty products, each with the same characteristics, for a new data collection. This data is then used to generate a third set of indicators, which are compared with the initial game and the simulation results, as part of our ongoing development process.

2.1 Purpose

The purpose of the digital twin used in this learning factory is to provide a practical application for the development of competencies in the design of processes with elements of innovation and under the concept of minimum viable product (MVP). This involves the construction of a process with minimum functions and the lowest possible cost that allows adjustments to achieve better performance in mass production with a spatial configuration in line. With this premise, the learning outcome of the proposed learning factory was that the students were able to make decisions in the design of the manufacturing process for the improvement of the management indicators of a serial production system with spatial configuration in line; for this, the achievement of some achievement indicators are considered.:

- Calculate performance measures for productivity (quantity of products, cycle time per unit, operation time per unit, and total manufacturing time of the production batch) and quality (number of defective and non-defective products).
- Set up a model of production system management indicators to compare production systems suitable for evaluating each operation and the production system as a single element.
- Build a replicated computer simulation model of the initial production performed in a playful environment, which can be further modified to propose desired future scenarios.
- Replicate the calculation of performance measures in each of the digital factory's phases: initial game, simulated models, and game with improvements. This will establish significant differences between the different phases, which will be used to evaluate the effect of the actions taken.
- Modify the process design in the simulation and in the final prototype to obtain significant differences in the performance measures and the set of indicators of each stage of the development of the learning factory.

Therefore, this new learning scenario contrasts with traditional teaching methods that limit the development of competencies for challenges in current and future manufacturing scenarios (Cachay, Wennemer, Abele, & Tenberg, 2012).

2.2 Process

The process in the learning factory, according to the literature on the subject, includes multiple process stages that include various technical and administrative aspects; in this way, the learning factory proposal is a playful bet taken from the compendium of games of an educational institution in Colombia (GEIO research group -

Universidade Tecnológica de Pereira, 2009), in which an adaptation of simulation exercises performed in other contexts and taken to the learning environment present in the country is made.

This playful activity includes five process stations, which are performed manually by five participants who have the role of operators; it is noteworthy that each of these operations requires different fine motor skills, which makes the first problem to be overcome by the work teams is the selection of the right person to perform each of these operations according to their physical development conditions and an adequate level of concentration because they are repetitive operations in the placement of Lego® chips inside a covered container.

A second aspect that represents another challenge is the coordination of the line under the push configuration, which will generate inventories in process between the different process stations, in addition to having different manufacturing rhythms in the production batch that are generated from a Monte Carlo simulation which randomly generates the colors (four different colors) equiprobable of two Lego® chips that will contain a container with a lid for the fifty products to be made. Considering the above technical and organizational aspects of the recreational activity, the manufacturing process of the products follows the following manufacturing process in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Learning factory process for the initial prototype of the mass production system with in-line spatial configuration.

After this initial setup, the initial conditions of the manufacturing process in the learning factory are established. The process performance measures are determined in two dimensions: productivity (quantity of products, cycle time per unit, operation time per unit, and total manufacturing time of the production batch) and quality (number of defective and non-defective products); it is necessary to perform a statistical analysis to determine the input parameters for the simulation model which followed the steps detailed in Figure 3 for the process times, while for the quality dimension, the fraction of non-conforming products is established through the calculation of probabilities with a binomial probability distribution function.

After the estimation of the probability distributions with their respective parameters that represent the operation times in each process station, the simulation model is built in suitable software, for which SIMIO® has been selected in its version available for the date on which the execution of the learning factory has been carried out. This software selection has to do with its ease of use and its environment inspired by the flow of materials, which does not require linking different graphic elements to the simulation.

Figure 2. Simulation model for Simio® of the mass production system with in-line spatial configuration.

The formulation of the simulation model, which will be the digital twin, follows the process diagram shown in Figure 3 in the operation phase, incorporating the parameters and probability distributions in a model with five process stations, five buffers that represent the intermediate inventory between the process stations and the finished product warehouse, with which the group of students performs a validation process against the real twin, obtaining a representative result to finally start the experimentation process according to the possible changes described in the adjustments section of this document.

It is noteworthy that the digital twins are built by teams of students from different branches of engineering, who, through the different occupational profiles, contribute possible changes that can be implemented through a process that involves mediation, teamwork, and active participation; this process is done through techniques such as brainstorming and weighting exercises of alternatives and in some cases using online software for text analysis.

Figure 3. Data analysis process for information from the initial prototype of the learning factory.

Now, simultaneously, once the parameters of the probability distributions for the different operation times, the number of products produced, and the number of conforming and nonconforming products are, it is possible to build a model of process operation indicators in which a form of relationship of the performance measures is used in which it is possible to include a part or all of them, with which it is possible to characterize the behavior of each of the stages of the learning factory process: initial actual prototype or real twin, digital prototype in simulation or digital twin and final real prototype or digital twin and the real and digital master which is the final prototype, an example of the formulation of indicators is possible to see it in table 1.

These indicators evaluate production rates, batch sizes, and average times per manufactured unit, with which it is usually possible to evaluate the performance of a real production system generated from the learning factory, besides being a fundamental part of the formulation of the digital scenarios that are simulated, helping the evaluation of each one of them, discarding those with worse performance according to the directives that govern the game in terms of maximization of production volume, minimization of cycle times and impact of the change of outputs in the process design, as indicated in various models of evaluation of systems with a material flow such as factory physics, theory of constraints, among others.

Table 1. Model of indicators for the evaluation of the different phases of the learning factory and their comparison among themselves.

	Cycle time per batch (min)	Number of units completed (U1)	Number of Non-Compliant Units (U2)
Cycle time per batch (min)	1	$Cycle\ time\ unit = \frac{Min}{U1}$	$Arrival\ non\ compliant = \frac{Min}{U2}$
Number of units completed (U1)	$Rate\ production = \frac{U1}{min}$	1	$Size\ lot\ fraction\ add = \frac{U1}{U2}$
Number of Non-Compliant Units (U2)	$Rate\ production\ non\ compliant = \frac{U2}{min}$	$Non\ compliant\ fraction = \frac{U2}{U1}$	1

Finally, the process concludes with the selection of the digital twin to be implemented in the final prototype of the learning factory, which is made from the multidisciplinary analysis of engineering students with different profiles, which is performed by direct analysis of the differences of the performance measures and operation indicators by the last achievement indicator proposed by a set of teachers, to be subsequently implemented in the real prototype in which it is returned to real twin to test the simulated hypotheses in reality with its corresponding measurement and comparison with the initial phase and the simulation phase.

2.3 Settings

In this area, the proposed learning factory takes into account the concept of the literature on the subject, which consists of a changing environment that resembles a real value chain, which is represented through the possible changes that can be made in the initial configuration of the recreational activity in the scenarios to be simulated and the final prototype with changes, which can be defined as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Possible changes in the manufacturing process proposed in the learning factory.

Organizational level of changes	Possible changes
Strategic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in the production management system to JIT, CONWIP or other. • Addition of strategic objectives such as profit maximization, revenue, production volume, capacity utilization or cost minimization, and productive leisure. • Addition of new operations before or after the above processes.
Tactical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in the sequence of operations to manufacture the product. • Changes in the probability of occurrence of Lego® colors in the forecasted demand. • Use of downstream material flow coordination formats in the simulated value chain.
Operational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in workstation design in terms of orientation, location, and type of tools in each operation. • Changes in the ergonomics of the workstation in each operation in the initial environment start in a standing position. • Addition or reduction of resources such as operators at each process station. • Combining or separating operations by grouping them in new or eliminated process stations. • Use of Poka-Yoke elements to improve the sequence or fundamental elements of the method in each operation.

The above adjustments have been compiled from numerous executions with various groups of engineering students in regular courses ranging from the beginning of the program to the last semester in industrial engineering and the field of international professorship for students of systems engineering, mechatronics, mechanical, civil, electrical and electronics, as well as students of the health area in nutrition and nursing.

It is also useful to say that the adjustments in reference are not the only ones possible since the improvement of production processes is a continuous task that also involves the formulation of new alternatives and methods; this can be an opportunity for improvement in the learning factory by not having limitations on the number and type of changes.

2.4 Product

The proposed learning factory makes a simple product in five different operations. This product consists of a container that contains two Legos® inside. The first one is small, has four pins, and can have one of four colors selected for the exercise according to the availability of materials, while the other one is large, has eight pins, and has one of four colors available.

As the manufacturing process nears completion, the product is sealed with a hermetic lid, ensuring the integrity of the container. This sealed container houses two Legos® of different sizes and colors, often corresponding to the colors available. The product is then adorned with a sticker, meticulously painted with office elements in the same colors as the Legos® inside. This sticker is carefully aligned with a characteristic of the container, adding a final touch of precision.

The product quality characteristics to be verified in each unit are the hermetic seal of the container, the content of two Legos® of different sizes inside the container, the correct alignment of the sticker, and the correspondence of the colors of the sticker and the Legos® inside the container.

2.5 Didactic

Didactics are critical in implementing an active learning model, especially when teaching complex concepts such as push production systems. By incorporating a playful activity into the learning factory, such as a simulation game with a digital twin model, students can interact with realistic scenarios to experience the concepts in real-time. This hands-on experience facilitates understanding the principles underlying the push production system and its relationship with other components of the production process.

Students can assume specific roles within the production system in this activity, such as operators with different manual skills. Through simulation, students decide how to organize the production flow, manage available resources, and optimize the process to maximize efficiency and minimize waste. This dynamic fosters collaboration and teamwork, as students must coordinate their actions to achieve the objectives of the production system.

Using a digital twin model in the play activity allows students to see the results of their decisions in real time and adjust their strategy accordingly. This immediate feedback helps them better understand the consequences of their actions and develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In addition, the digital twin model provides a safe environment to experiment and learn from mistakes, which fosters innovation and adaptability in the learning process.

2.6 Operation model

The operation model allows to establish the desired continuous operation of the learning factory in this way, the proposed ludic activity has a plant distribution as shown in Figure 4 in which a sequence of the initial processes for the development of the digital twin is established, which has the opportunity of a great variety of possible changes that could not be listed in its entirety due to the complexity of the operation in the proposed serial process.

Figure 4. Facility layout with the operating model of the play activity in the proposed learning factory.

The first analysis that allows the operation model for the learning factory is the evaluation of changes through an analysis of operations and methods with traditional methods described in the literature, followed by an analysis of workstations, and ergonomics, among other aspects, to subsequently perform analysis of required and available capacity by type of resource, task scheduling or finally perform analysis of production management systems and incorporation of techniques specific to each of these.

These analyses incorporate numerous concepts and technical tools that when implemented in the digital model can obtain diverse and valuable results that allow to have different experiences in each team of participants when shared indicate paths with solutions sometimes not treated traditionally but that work in the reality of the educational model.

Figure 5 shows some images of the execution of this initial operation model by working groups of the engineering faculty of the National University of Colombia in Bogotá, D.C., Colombia.

Figure 5. (a) Play activity in the product assembly process according to the operation model described. (b) Experimentation exercise of different scenarios with the simulation software in use. (c) Socialization of results of the designed learning factory exercise

3 Results

Finally, the results of this article consist of the presentation of a teaching methodology for rapid prototyping in process design, consisting of six steps, which were achieved from a methodology used for the construction of meaningful experiences for learning factories. (Abele, y otros, 2017; Dahl, Tvenge, Assuad, & Martinsen, 2023), in which the concepts of purpose, process, settings, product, didactics, and operating model described in the article are included.

Thus, the methodology achieved is integrated by a playful activity at the beginning and end of the activity, followed by two moments of measurement of variables in reality and the simulation model, two moments of evaluation of alternatives under process design precepts in the simulation model and the final playful activity, and a moment of contrast of measurements to determine the degree of change between the initial and final condition of the production plant as defined in Figure 6.

Finally, by working with different groups of industrial, mechatronics, mechanical, chemical, and systems engineering students, it was possible to observe changes in the configuration of the production system in three fundamental aspects:

- Changes in installed capacity in each of the process stations, by adding, deleting, or repositioning the number of operators assigned to each process station to perform a process line balancing process and decrease process inventories without affecting operating times in each process station.
- Changes in the materials, tools, transformation methods, and arrangement of the workstations for each station which it was achieved the reduction of operation times in each one of the transformations reducing the cycle time of elaboration of a production lot with a minor impact in the inventories of material in process.
- Changes in the manufacturing sequence by making a new process that has achieved a decrease in the operation times in each process station and the inventories of material in process, being this one of the most radical changes that have worked in the improvement of the process design in the prototyping stage.

It is noteworthy that many groups have achieved other types of changes that have not had significant changes between the initial condition of the learning plant and the one obtained at the end of the exercise, these changes have also had feedback as possible changes that have not affected the result of the prototype of the learning plant, an aspect that has served as an element of control and test of the improvement hypothesis.

Figure 6. Teaching methodology for prototyping in process design.

4 Discussion

The success of the playful activity with digital twins highlights the importance of integrating advanced technologies into education, especially in fields related to production and industry. By combining active learning approaches with case study methodologies, students can relate theory to practice more meaningfully and retentively.

The concept-based approach formulated by Abele et al. (2017) and Dahl, Tvenge, Assuad, and Martinsen (2023) provided a sound structure for designing the pedagogical activity, ensuring that all key aspects of learning and development are addressed. This structure also facilitates evaluating the effectiveness of the activity and provides a framework for future improvements. However, it is crucial to recognize that the success of this activity depends on several factors, such as the quality of the simulation, the instructors' preparedness, and the student's willingness to participate actively in the learning process. In addition, the implementation of digital twin technologies may require a significant investment in resources and training, which may be a challenge for some educational institutions, which may have an alternative to this activity using low-cost materials and a free academic simulator, which may be accessible and beneficial for institutions with limited resources without reaching a high level of automation.

5 Conclusions

The digital twin model based on a playful activity has proven to be an effective tool for teaching thrust production systems. Students were able to experience a simulated environment in which the six key concepts relating to learning and development of the pedagogical device were applied: purpose, process, settings, product, didactics, and operating model. This allowed students to develop a deeper understanding of the principles of thrust production and how they apply them in a real-world context. The use of a digital twin provided students with immediate feedback on their decisions, allowing them to adjust their strategies in real time and improve their performance on the production system. In addition, the model allowed for a collaborative, hands-on learning experience, fostering teamwork and the development of problem-solving and critical-thinking skills. In summary, the playful activity using digital twins for teaching push production systems has not only been an enriching educational experience for students but has also proven to be an effective methodology for facilitating the understanding and application of complex production concepts.

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